

PROSPECTS FOR USING MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation: *The article examines the pedagogical aspects, importance and effectiveness of the use of mobile applications in higher education. The classical components of the educational process are highlighted, taking into account the basics of professional and pedagogical activity. However, as a result of empirical research, the demand for the use of mobile applications in the educational process has been studied and statistical analysis has been conducted and conclusions have been drawn.*

Keywords: *mobile education, mobile technology, pedagogy, Google form, survey.*

In higher education, teachers and students have a good understanding of mobile education and are ready to accept it. Although the introduction of mobile technologies in the educational process is underway, the main reason for the lack of high performance in this area is the lack of development of mobile applications with educational content, which means that there is a need for research in this area . . In addition, most of the existing educational mobile applications are designed to organize foreign language learning and testing. Mobile applications of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan are almost non-existent, although reputable foreign higher education institutions pay serious attention to this. Nevertheless, pedagogical staff and students of higher education use mobile devices during their activities often they use. Although the laptop is also a widely used device, mobile devices dominate when it comes to numbers and internet connection and access to educational resources. Mobile technology plays an important role in planning day-to-day activities related to education.

Given the current and future relevance of mobile education, and as a basis for the above, the study, which includes the study of the level of use of mobile education and mobile applications among teachers and students of higher education institutions in

Uzbekistan was held. It asks teachers and students of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan to apply to the questionnaire and answer questions via <https://forms.gle/UUTJg7HardXKdQKx9>.

The questionnaire consists of 9 questions, each of which includes answer options, only one of which requires you to choose more than one or write a personal opinion. The survey questions are aimed at identifying the following three aspects:

Figure 1. 3 aspects to be identified using a survey.

The survey consists of 9 questions of different types developed in the Google Form environment. The overall proportion of respondents is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 . Graphical view of the ratio of survey participants.

The next question in the survey was “What types of devices do you use most in your educational activities?” to the question, most users noted that they use laptops and personal smartphones (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Use of equipment by teachers and students of higher education institutions. A) Personal computer; B) Laptop; C) Tablet; D) Smartphone.

Participants reported that most use mobile technology in planning their day-to-day activities related to education.

By conducting a comparative analysis of the results of the survey in tabular form, we see evidence that teachers and students are increasingly using mobile learning technologies in their educational activities.

As mobile technology continues to grow, policymakers will need to reconsider ICT opportunities for education. These suggestions are designed to facilitate the process of implementing the most preferred education policy by detailing some of the unique benefits of mobile education and providing advice.

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